

DEGRADATION OF ACONITINE

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On oxidation with aluminium *tert.*-butoxide, aconitine yields a product, aconitinone. The latter on heating produces a methoxyl-free compound, designated as aconitoline, which has been shown to be an $\alpha\beta$ -unsaturated ketone from its U. V. and I. R. spectra. An infra-red absorption spectrum of pyroaconitine reveals that pyrolysis of aconitine proceeds through the formation of an ethylenic linkage and not an epoxy group. Pyrolytic products obtained at a higher temperature are also described.

This communication outlines the results of a study of the oxidation of aconitine with aluminium *tert.*-butoxide and its pyrolysis at different temperatures, the principal aim of which is to establish the mechanisms of these reactions.

In aconitine, $C_{34}H_{47}O_{11}N$, aluminium *tert.*-butoxide specifically oxidises one secondary hydroxyl to a carbonyl group. The resulting product, aconitinone ($C_{34}H_{45}O_{11}N$), on heating readily splits off a molecule of methanol, yielding a base, aconitoline, $C_{32}H_{41}O_{10}N$. The latter contains in its ultraviolet absorption curve maxima at $232\text{ m}\mu$ ($\log \epsilon 4.1$) and $274\text{ m}\mu$ ($\log \epsilon 2.83$) which are characteristics of an $\alpha\beta$ -unsaturated ketone (Gillman and Stern, "An Introduction to Electronic Absorption Spectroscopy in Organic Chemistry", Edward Arnold Publishers, London, 1954, p. 90), and thus confirm the following mode of reaction proposed by Majima and Tamura (*Annalen*, 1940, 545, 1). The latter was also prepared from aconitine by its oxidation with chromic acid.

The presence of an $\alpha\beta$ -unsaturated ketone in aconitoline is further confirmed by the fact that its infra-red spectrum exhibits a strong band at 5.97μ .

On pyrolysis just above the melting point (205°), aconitine loses one molecule of acetic acid, furnishing pyroaconitine, $C_{32}H_{43}O_9N$. The mechanism by which this reaction takes place has not been settled (Manske and Holmes, "The Alkaloids", Vol. IV, 1954, pp. 296-299). Pyroaconitine has been assumed to contain either an epoxy group, created by elimination of acetic acid between the acetoxy group and an adjacent hydroxyl (Dunstan and Carr, *J. Chem. Soc.*, 1894, 65, 178; Schulze and Liebner, *Arch. Pharm.*, 1913, 251, 453; 1916, 284, 567) or an ethylenic linkage analogous to pyro- α -oxodelphinine (Jacobs and Huebner, *J. Biol. Chem.*, 1947, 170, 209).

However, infra-red spectroscopy offers a very promising approach towards the clarification of this mechanism. Absorption spectrum of aconitine (Nath, this *Journal*, 1955, 32, 25) contains a strong band at 6.02μ due to a non-conjugated double bond. But pyroaconitine does not exhibit in its absorption curve any band at 6.02μ , but instead a doublet near $6.22\text{--}6.33\mu$, showing definite diene conjugation. This could only arise if a new ethylenic linkage is introduced in the conjugated position to that initially present during pyrolysis by abstraction of a molecule of acetic acid between the ester grouping and a hydrogen atom from a neighbouring carbon atom. Thus, the mode of elimination of acetic acid is through an olefinic linking and not *via* an epoxide. This conclusion has been supported by catalytic hydrogenation experiment of pyroaconitine when it shows an uptake of approximately 5 moles of hydrogen, 3 moles due to benzoyl group and two moles due to two C=C bonds.

It is of interest to record that when pyrolysis of aconitine is effected at $250\text{--}60^\circ/2$ mm, the elimination of acetic acid is followed by deposition of :

(i) A colorless sublimate (A) consisting of needles, $C_7H_6O_2$, m.p. $122\text{--}24^\circ$. It does not contain nitrogen. It is acidic in character. Its ultraviolet absorption curve has a maximum at $228\text{ m}\mu$ ($\log \epsilon 4.08$) and an inflexion at $272\text{ m}\mu$ ($\log \epsilon 3.06$). The infra-red absorption spectrum possesses bands at 3.78μ , 5.98μ , 7.60μ , 7.84μ and 10.78μ , probably due to an acid.

(ii) A pale yellow resin (B), m.p. $108\text{--}110^\circ$. Its U. V. absorption spectrum has a maximum at $230\text{ m}\mu$ ($\log \epsilon 3.96$) and infra-red curve contains, besides many common bands with the parent substance, aconitine, some bands at 6.39μ and 6.48μ .

EXPERIMENTAL

Infra-red Absorption Spectra.—The data recorded were obtained with a Grubb-Parsons single-beam absorption spectrophotometer having a sodium chloride prism. All the above substances were examined in a solution of known concentration in purified CCl_4 in the region 2.8μ to 7μ and in CS_2 in the region 7μ to 15μ in a rock salt cell having a capacity of 0.1 c.c.

Oxidation of Aconitine : (a) With Al-tert.-butoxide.—A mixture of aconitine (0.5 g.), aluminium *tert.*-butoxide (1.5 g.), dry cyclohexanone (20 c.c.) and dry toluene (70 c.c.) was refluxed for 6 hours. After cooling, the suspension was extracted with 10% H_2SO_4 . The acid extract was washed several times with ether to remove cyclohexanone and then treated with an excess of 20% NaOH solution and extracted with ether; the ethereal extract was dried (anhydrous Na_2SO_4) and the solvent removed when a slightly pink residue was obtained. This was crystallised from ethyl acetate, m. p. $148\text{--}49^\circ$. (Found : C, 63.4; H, 6.7. Calc. for $C_{24}H_{45}O_{11}N$: C, 63.5; H, 7.0%).

The above product aconitinone (0.1 g.) was dissolved in methanol (10 c.c.) and the solution refluxed for 1 hour. After reducing the volume to one third, it was chilled when a small quantity of a flocculent precipitate separated, m.p. 220° . (Found : C, 64.5; H, 7.3. Calc. for $C_{23}H_{42}O_{10}N$: C, 64.9; H, 6.8%).

(b) *With Chromic Acid.*—Aconitine (1.5 g.) was dissolved in acetone (90 c.c.) and cooled in an ice-salt mixture. To this was added a cooled solution of chromic anhydride (1.5 g.) and water (0.75 g.) in acetone (15 c.c.). After keeping the mixture at 15° for 10 days the solvent was removed in vacuo, the residue dissolved in sulphurous acid and extracted with ether. The aqueous layer was made alkaline with sodium carbonate and the precipitated base collected. This was crystallised from ethyl acetate, m.p. 149-50° and its mixed m.p. with the above aconitine, 149-50°, was undepressed.

Pyrolysis of Aconitine—Aconitine (0.2 g.) was heated as 203-205°/2 mm for 1 hour and the residue (pyroaconitine) crystallised from a mixture of ether and light petroleum, m. p. 169-70°. (Found: C, 65.8; H, 6.9. Calc. for $C_{32}H_{48}O_9N$: C, 65.6; H, 7.3%).

Hydrogenation.—Pyroaconitine (15.4 mg.) was hydrogenated with platinum oxide catalyst (30 mg.) in ethanol containing a drop of HCl. The process was completed in 2 hours with an absorption of hydrogen (found: 2.8 c.c., calc. ~ 4.6 moles). After removing the catalyst and the solvent, the product was crystallised from ethanol, m. p. 162°. (Found: C, 64.9; H, 8.5. Calc. for $C_{32}H_{52}O_9N$: C, 64.5; H, 8.9%).

In another experiment aconitine (1.1 g.) was first heated at 205°/2 mm and after an hour the temperature was raised to 250-260°/2 mm, furnishing (A) and (B).

(A): A colorless sublimate in the form of needles, m.p. 122-24°. [Found: C, 68.9; H, 4.86; M.W. 130 (Rast). $C_7H_8O_2$ requires C, 68.8; H, 4.9%. M.W. 122].

(B): A pale yellow resin, m.p. 108-10°, also sublimed and its composition was found to be C, 63.95; H, 7.5; N, 2.9%. It could not be induced to crystallise from any solvent.

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